

NIGERIAN ENGLISH: A VARIETY WITHOUT A STANDARD

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Abstract

English is used as a second language in Nigeria and unarguably, it is expected to be influenced by the Nigerian indigenous languages. For Nigerians to adequately use it to express their socio-cultural and political experiences. Thus, its nativization and indigenization is inevitable. However, this is expected to be done within the ambit of the rules considered the world by identification standard. This paper, therefore, working on the data collected from grammatical 600 students of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, Lanlate Campus, reveals that Nigerian English is characterized by violation of grammatical rules, damaging of grammatical structures and distortion of meanings. It therefore concludes that efforts should be made by the eminent linguists in Nigeria to codify Nigerian English (NE) so as to be able to sift the Nigeria usages from the correct ones. This will accord it (NE) international recognition and Nigerian users will be saved from embarrassment in the midst of international speakers.

Keywords: Nigerian English, Variety and Standard.

Introduction

A lot of things have been written on the reality/existence of Nigerian English (NE). While some scholars are of the opinion that Nigerian English has come to stay and there is nothing we can do about it (e.g. Banjo, 1995; Bamgbose, 1971, 2004; Akere 1982; Afolayan 1987 and Ogunsiji, 2004), many more are of the opinion that caution should be taken in using NE especially for teaching and learning processes (Salami, 1968, Adesanoye,

1973, Adetugbo, 1979, Akere, 1982 and Kujore, 1985). However, in the words of Adedigba (2004), researches are expected to continue in the areas of Nigerian English, since much still has to be done on it. For instance, as observed by Akinjobi (2002) and Banjo (1995) among other scholars who have written on Nigerian English. there is "absence of standard grammar books and reference materials to which to turn for what constitutes correct and acceptable usages in NE, and what does not" (Igboanusi, 2002). It is therefore our interest in this paper to beam our searchlight on the quality or variety of English spoken and written by Nigerians in order to show its (lack of) standard. This will be done, as suggested by Adedigba (2004), based on - not only what is adjudged correct by English as Mother Tongue (EMT) standards (e.g. British English or American English) but acceptable to the international or World English audience. It is our belief that, since English is now a world language, if we cannot but use Nigerian English at all, it should not be without a standard. We are not against Bamgbose's (2004) assertion that nativization of English in Nigeria is unavoidable.

English as a Global Language

No one can resist the dominance of the English language in the world today. It is a world language and in the words of Halliday (2003), "those who are able to exploit it, whether to sell goods and services or to sell ideas, wield enormous power" (Pp-13). As reported by Ofuya (1999), English is spoken by over 400 million peoples as a mother tongue in Britain, most parts of the United States of America and Canada, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa and many parts of the West, it is spoken by another over 400 million people as a second language in many countries of the world, especially those that were formerly under British Empire, while it is the most preferred foreign language in the European Mainland, die Middle East and in many parts of Asia and South America.

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In support of Ofuya (1999), Oyeleye (2005), submits that English is currently being used along side native languages in even European countries and its domains of use increase significantly daily. In the same vein, Ayodele (2004) reports that in a Survey recently conducted in the European countries, as to which language they would prefer, as many as 93% indicated English. He finally concludes that in continental European schools i.e. where English is not the mother tongue, English is studied as a second language. From the foregoing, it is obvious that English is spreading at a very fast rate, and since it is the most widely used language in the world, it will undoubtedly be affected or influenced by the native languages of those who use it as either their second or foreign language, thus naturally, it would have many varieties.

Coming back to Nigeria, considering all things, one would not be wrong to say that English is a second language. It is learnt by a child right from his formative years. It is the language most children come in contact with even before going to school through their parents or other people they live with or by listening to the radio or television. It is a language in which children acquire the education right from the upper primary school till the end of their education, and a language in which the decisions and affairs that affect their lives are conducted.

In Nigeria today, English is the language of governance and administration, the language of the judiciary, especially from the high court, to the Supreme Court. It is the language in which most of the newspapers and magazines are written. Concerning the electronic media, it is the language in which the major national issues are presented and in which most forms of entertainment meant for wider, national audience are presented.

Taking the role and status of English in Nigeria into cognizance, therefore, we need to be mindful of the form of English we speak and write. It

is certain that, because English is a second language in Nigeria, it will come in contact with and be influenced by the Nigerian indigenous languages. To express our socio-cultural and political realities, new words and expressions are bound to be introduced into it i.e. English would be given a new face, it would be nativized or indigenized, but it should have a standard: it should not be bent to the extent of making it a completely different variety from the one used in its ancestral home. It should not be to the extent that it (NE) will be seen' as a bundle of errors by the native/competent users of the language and Nigerian speakers will be making a fool of themselves in the community of speakers of the language from other nations of the world. As advocated by some linguists, it should have both social acceptability and international intelligibility (Banjo 1995, Igboanusi, 2002, Akinjobi 2002 and Bamgbose 2004).

Motivation for and Source of Data

As an English Language Lecturer at the college of Education and being a person that believes in strict compliance with the rules of English as used by the native speakers of the language, it has been observed to a great disappointment that, the written English of most students of the College is nothing to write home about. And undoubtedly, the quality of their English is a reflection of the quality of NE spoken by the averagely educated Nigerians.

A mini study was earlier conducted by the written English of ENG 125, a year one Course titled Introduction to Modern African Literature and GSE 302, a year 3 general course in English comprising 100 and 500 students respectively. A class test and an assignment were given to each of the two classes of students and taking them as representing the fairly educated members of the larger society, the data used for this paper were got from their answers. The data were classified based on the nature of errors committed by them. The features of their English taken to be the features of

Their English taken to be the features of NE spoken by the larger percentage of the macro society are discussed below.

Special Features of Nigerian English in Our Data

Several attempts have been made by scholars to describe/discuss the features or character of Nigerian English (Banjo 1999, Bamgbose 1971 and 2004 & Akindele and Adegbite, 1999) as well as the need to further intensify research in this area. For instance, Bamgbose (1971) highlights features of Nigerian Bamgbos that have been identified and discussed by some scholars. Such features which manifest at all levels of linguistic analysis include: substitution of Nigerian language vowels and consonants for English ones, replacement of stress by tone, pluralization of some noncount/mass nouns, introduction of culture-specific vocabulary items, backformation, semantic shift, etc. Most of these features are also identified by Banjo (1995) and Akindele and Adegbite (1999). We want to say from the outset that though it is not our intention to engage in meaningless repetition of the grounds already covered by others, a number of the features identified in our data have been identified by some scholars in their works. The features identified in our data are discussed below, though our emphases are on lexis, meaning (semantics) and syntax.

(i) Confusion of British and American Lexical Items

Although a large number of the students are familiar with the commonly used British and American words such as centre/center, colour/color, behaviour/behavior, transportation/transport, programme /program, etc., most of them confuse the use of words like ill/sick, flat/apartment. Cooker/stove, taxi/cab, driving licence/driver's licence, etc.

They can hardly distinguish the two sets of words, from the way they used the words in their essays. They do not know that the first of every pair of the items is British while the second of every pair is an American word. Let us, for instance, consider some of their sentences to illustrate this.

- (a) My parents are living in an apartment at Ibadan while Fin living in a flat with four other students here.
- (b) I'm tired of using a stove; I must find a means of getting money to buy a cooker.

From the two sentences above, it is obviously clear that most of our subjects (students) believe that an apartment is bigger than a flat, while a cooker is more sophisticated than a stove. In fact, out of ignorance, some of them believe that a stove uses kerosene while a cooker uses electricity.

(ii) **Ascribing Wrong Meanings to English Words**

Possibly out of poor acquisition of English right from the primary school or exposure to badly written text books on English, a large number of the wrongs subjects attach wrong meanings to some English words. Consideration of some of these sentences where wrong meanings are wrong attached to English words will suffice.

- (a) i will travel abroad immediately after my graduation from here.
- (b) Nigerian politicians collect bogus salaries while the teachers are suffering.
- (c) I will buy my food stuff from my customer.
- (d) The girl is too local for my liking
- (e) The man lives in a house that is adjacent to ours.
- (f) That man is a dupe; you need to be careful in dealing with him.

Wrong meanings are attached to some words in the sentences above. For instance, Wrong meaning in sentence (a) is narrowed down to 'any advanced Country' instead of "any foreign Country" in Standard English,

while in sentence (b) the meaning of the word "bogus" is distorted to mean "fat" or "handsome" instead of "fake" in Standard English. On the other hand, in (c) "customer" is extended to "a seller" instead of "buyer" in Standard English, while in (d) the word "local" is used to mean "crude" or "not sophisticated" instead of the Standard English meaning of "concerning a particular place". Finally, in sentence (f), the word "dupe" is used to mean "he who cheats or a trickster" while in Standard English it means "the deceived".

From the analysis done so far, it is clear that certain features of Nigerian English conflict with those of Standard English. As observed by Igboanusi (2002), there may be the problem that relates to the issues of international intelligibility and how to be intelligible to foreigners visiting Nigeria. This fear is also possibly in Fakoya (2004) when he contends that "since English is not really a native language in Nigeria, language eria, it is expected to have its references in at least one international standard."

Many more examples of words that are given meanings different from Standard English still abound in our data. Some respondents also used "chemist" to mean a drug store/pharmacy instead of the Standard English meaning of "pharmacist", or "druggist", while "a troubleshooter" who is a peacemaker in Standard English is used to mean "a ti-OLiblemaker" by some of our subjects. What an awry and contradictory meaning! As earlier implied, this probably results from imperfect acquisition of the language from the primary school or what Adegbija (1989) calls standardization of idiosyncrasies of errors. Interestingly, some of the embarrassing words are used even by some educated Nigerians the embarrassing Nigerian way our subjects use them. Taking the setting from which our data were collected as a micro society, one may not be far from the truth to say that that is the way most Nigerians use them.

(iii) **Wrong Use of Adjectives**

As it happens in the larger society, most of our subjects also use some adjectives wrongly. The use of some adjectives is ridiculously embarrassing in that they do not exist in standard British or American English after which we expect Nigerian English to be patterned. Consideration of some of these sentences will suffice here for better and clearer illustration:

- (a) The baby has a running nose (for runny)
- (b) Many secondary school students are indiscipline.(for undisciplined)
- (c) Kola is trickish (for tricky)
- (d) She is always making insulting remarks (for insulting)
- (e) TUnde is a matured man (for mature)
- (f) John is a rascal boy (for rascally)

From the examples above, it is obvious that Nigerians use some adjectives wrongly out of ignorance or imperfect representing wrong of the language. We can see that in sentence (a) "running" is used instead of the language Standard English word "runny", in (b) "indiscipline" is used instead of "undisciplined", in (c) "trickish" is used instead of "tricky" while in (d) and (e), "insultive" and "matured" are wrongly used instead of "insulting" and "mature" respectively. What a variety without a standard.

(iv) **Senseless repetition of words**

This is also a feature identified in the written essays of our subjects. Some words and phrases were senselessly unnecessarily repeated. For instance, they gave sentences like:

- a. We arrived at Ibadan at 9.00a.m. in the morning
- b. Should in case, you see Tunji, tell him I have something to discuss with him.

This will undoubtedly be ridiculous to the international speakers of English. The writer here does not know that a.m. the abbreviated form of the

Latin phrase *ante meridian*, means "before midday/in the morning", he therefore ignorantly adds "in the morning to it morning (a.m.). Similarly, in the (b) sentence, he uses both 'should" and *'in case" instead of using either of the two. And this is a feature of Nigerian English that has been identified by some scholars. In fact, features that are worse than the ones here have been identified by some scholars (Akindele and Adegbite, 1999 and Ogunsiji 2004).

(v) Errors of Concord

Errors of concord are also discovered in our data. We, for instance, have sentences like:

- a. All work and no play make Jack a dull boy.
- b. Slow and steady always win the race
- c. The minutes of the last meeting was not read.

In the first two sentences i.e. (a) and (b), plural verbs are wrongly used instead of Singular verbs (makes and wins) because the writer sees the sentences as having two subjects each ("All work" and "no play" as the subject of (a) and "slow" and "steady" as the subjects of (b) instead of taking the two as a unit.

On the other hand, the subject of sentence (c) can be seen as singular in spite of the addition of the plural marker "s", thus, he uses a singular verb, "was". Nigerian English usage singular English usage requires a standard that will help to distinguish what is right from what is not. As Akinjobi (2002) puts it, the "common point of reference will help us to distinguish the errors from the accepted usages."

(vi) Deletion of Letters or Morpheme

Deletion of letter(s) or morpheme is another feature of Nigerian English discovered in Our data. In this case, the words are used as they are used in the Standard British English but possibly out of ignorance or lack of familiarity with their right usage, the final letter(s) of the words are deleted. And, this at times necessitates the use of the wrong verb form, especially when the words function at the subject position. Consideration of some

examples will suffice here.

- a. His whereabouts is unknown.
- b. He was caught unaware.
- c. We live oil the outskirts of the town.
- d. They could serve as summon on Chief Ojo.

We can see from the sentences a-d above that, instead of using, "whereabouts" "unawares", "outskirts" and "summons", the final letter "s" is deleted to have "whereabout", "unware", "OLitskirt" and "summon".

(vii) Errors in idioms

It is also discovered in our data that the Standard English idioms are damaged by English Nigerian users of English. In some cases, Standard English words are substituted and in other Nigerian letters are accidentally or intentionally deleted being ignorant of the fact that most idioms are fixed and any alteration/modification will betray the incompetence of the users. Let us consider some idioms to establish this finding:

- a. We went into the office turn by turn (instead of "in turn").
- b. All things being equal (instead of "other things being equal").
- c. What is good for the goose is good for the gander (instead of "What is sauce for the goose is sauce for the gander")
- d. I cracked my brain to answer the question (instead of "I racked my brain.")
- e. The office is out of bound to the students (instead of "out of bounds to the Students").
- f. I haven't seen him for donkey years (instead of "I haven't seen him for donkey's years).

From the sentences above, it can be seen that certain word(s) of the Standard English idioms are substituted for other words. For instance, "in turn" in Standard English is substituted for "turn by turn" in (a) "other things" is substituted for "all things" (b) "sauce" is substituted for "good" in (c), while "racked" is substituted for things in (d). On the other hand, in sentences M and (f) letters are deleted. "Bound" is used in (e) instead of "bounds" while "donkey" is used in (f) instead of "donkey's" in Standard British English. The question now is, in a bid of using Nigerian English, shall we now use the damaged idioms which may be acceptable to the Nigerians or the Standard English forms that are internationally acceptable?

Conclusion

So far, we have been able to argue that realizing the fact that English is now a global/international language, considering the rate at which it spreads, we therefore need to gauge the variety/varieties of English we use in Nigeria, particularly the written English. Expectedly, as argued by Bamgbose (1971 & 2004), Igboanusi (2002), Akinjobi (2002) and Egwuagu (2004) among other eminent scholars, it is all impossible ideal to insist that Standard Nigerian English should be devoid of any markers of nativization, for these constitute the idiosyncratic features that separate Nigerian English from other varieties of English all over the world. Acceptably, language is embedded in the culture of a people, which in turn encompasses their total worldview. Nigerians are therefore expected to bend and twist the English language to reflect their socio-cultural, political and economic experiences. In the words of Soyinka (1988) cited in Banjo (1995), Nigerians need to stretch the language, stretch it, impact it and compact it, fragment and reassemble it with no apology to express perfectly what could not have been expressed by Standard British English but, which are relevant to the day-to-day interpersonal verbal interaction of the people.

However, as persistently cautioned by some scholars (Adeniran, 1979, Adesanoye 1973; Adetugbo 1979; Akere 1982, Kujore 1985 and Adedigba 2004) in characterizing and identifying Nigerian English as all English as a second language variety, it has to be nativised/indigenized in such a way that its Standard features will accommodate not only those that are adjudged correct by EMT standards (such as British and American English), but acceptable to the international world English audience. In fact, Adedigba (2004), bluntly submits that "it is necessary to separate the non-standard forms from the standard features". Fakoya (2004) also toeing the line of Adebite, argues that realizing the fact that all toeing ID argues realizing speakers of English, whether as first, second or foreign language, have a role to play in its development and growth, however, while performing the linguistic operation through cultural deployment of the language, users still have to align themselves to standard usage.

Some linguists like Igboanusi (2002) contend that the issues of international intelligibility and how to be intelligible to foreigners visiting Nigeria should be played down, and that those visiting Nigeria should be ready to make some sacrifice to get familiar with the Nigerian variety. It should however be realized that, Nigerian English is a variety of a language, it is therefore imperative for its users to seek recognition beyond their socio-cultural community. Even Banjo (1995) stressed the twin criteria of social acceptability and international intelligibility in the choice of appropriate model/variety of Nigeria English.

Our submission here therefore is that, it is high time Nigerian English had a standard. Nigerian English should not be seen as a bundle of errors. Unarguably, native speaker competence is unrealistic and counter productive for non-native speakers (Banjo, 1995, Gnutzmann, 1999 and Bamgbose, 2004). As submitted by Achebe when asked if an African could ever learn to use English as an Englishman, "it is necessarily, not desirable for him to do so"

so" (Achebe, 1975 cited by Igboanusi 2002). Since English is now a world language, its various users now have the freedom to bend and shape it to reflect correctly their life experiences. The freedom should however be exploited with a limit; it should not be extended to the point of breaking or violating the rules of its grammar, damaging its violating or distorting its meanings. As contended by Graddol (1997), the use of English as a global lingual franca, requires intelligibility and the setting and maintaining of standard. Nigerian English needs a standard that will help in sifting the errors from the unavoidable variations. For long now, scholars have been clamouring for its standardization and codification, but up till now, nothing substantial has been done about it. Banjo (1995) discussed about efforts being directed at producing a monolingual dictionary that will deal basically with standard Nigerian usage. 'It is twenty-eight years now and the dictionary is yet to be out. We commend the effort of Igboanus (2002) at producing A Dictionary of Nigerian English Usage, but I doubt its availability to the English language teachers not to talk of the generality of the people. Nigerian English is a variety without a standard yet.

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